

Heisenberg's and Hardy's uncertainty principles for special relativistic space-time Fourier transformation

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To Mrs. El Haoui.

Abstract. The special relativistic (space-time) Fourier transform (SFT) in Clifford algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ of space-time, first introduced from a mathematical point of view in [9], extends the quaternionic Fourier transform to functions, fields and signals in space-time. The purpose of this paper is to advance the study of the SFT and investigate important properties such as continuity, Plancherel identity, Riemann-Lebesgue lemma, and to establish the associated Hausdorff-Young inequality. Moreover, using the observer related space-time split several uncertainty inequalities are established, including Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and Hardy's theorem.

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1. Introduction

In mathematical physics, it is well known that the theory of special relativity introduced by Albert Einstein, formerly student of the German mathematician Hermann Minkowski, is ideally studied in the context of a four-dimensional space, known as the Minkowski space-time $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ [21].

In addition to electromagnetism, for which it was initially developed, Minkowski space-time has been shown to be a prevalent mathematical concept for a multitude of physical phenomena in space and time.

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Furthermore, the Clifford algebra [24, 5] over Minkowski space-time is an ideal framework for unifying classical and quantum physics, optics, provides a new theory for gravity, cosmology, radio astronomy, etc. [6, 7, 19]. Since the Fourier transform and more recently the Clifford Fourier transform [15] is a vital tool in optics, (color) image analysis, non-marginal signal processing, computer graphics and pattern recognition [16], mathematicians and physicists are interested in formulating and applying the Fourier transform in the context of the Clifford algebra over Minkowski space-time.

In this way, the second author [9] generalized the concept of quaternion Fourier transform QFT to a full space-time Fourier transformation (SFT) for 16-dimensional space-time algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ -valued signals starting with the algebra isomorphism between \mathbb{H} , the algebra of quaternions, and $Cl_{(3,0)}^+$ the volume-time sub-algebra of the Clifford geometric algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ of $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, spanned by the four dimensional basis $\{1, e_t, i_3, i_{st}\}$.

We denote with

$$\{e_t, e_1, e_2, e_3\}, \quad -e_t^2 = e_1^2 = e_2^2 = e_3^2 = 1, \quad (1.1)$$

the orthonormal vector basis for $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, where the spatial unit volume trivector i_3 and the pseudo-scalar i_{st} can be expressed by

$$i_3 = e_1 e_2 e_3, \quad i_3^2 = -1, \quad i_{st} = e_t i_3, \quad i_{st}^2 = -1, \quad (1.2)$$

respectively.

Moreover, the second author [9] applied the spacetime split to space-time multi-vectors functions, and gave a physical interpretation to this split as generating terms of left and right traveling multivector wave packets, creating a special relativistic multivector wave packet analysis framework.

As with quaternion algebra [4] and other Clifford algebras [18], the non-commutativity of the multivector product leads to two and more resulting terms of the convolution product of multivector valued functions, all with their own important symmetry properties. Therefore, recently the (classical) convolution of space-time signals was defined, as well as their Mustard convolution in terms of the space-time Clifford algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ [19]. In our current work we contribute to the development of this new area of applied harmonic analysis, namely hyper-complex transforms, by providing several new properties associated with space-time multivector valued signals, and dealing with the extension to the space-time Fourier transform domain of classical results such as Plancherel identity, uniform continuity, Riemann-Lebesgue lemma, the image of a Gaussian, etc. Additionally, based on the orthogonal split of space-time algebra, we establish uncertainty inequalities including the Hausdorff-Young inequality, Heisenberg's inequality and Hardy's theorem for the SFT.

We expect our results to be of great utility in the advancement of the mathematical notion of space-time Fourier transform and its potentially wide ranging applications in many branches of physics, computer science, graphics, artificial intelligence and engineering.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 briefly reviews the Clifford geometric algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ over the Minkowski vector space $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$. Then Section 3 introduces the space-time Fourier transform (SFT) and several of its important properties. Finally, Section 4 establishes Heisenberg's and Hardy's uncertainty principles for the SFT. The paper concludes with Section 5 followed by Acknowledgments and References.

2. Definition and Properties of Space-Time Algebra

Let $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_t\}$ be the orthonormal basis of the real vector space $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ as given in (1.1).

The space-time algebra over $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, denoted by $Cl_{(3,1)}$, is defined as an associative, non-commutative algebra which has a 16-dimensional graded basis:

$$\{1, e_t, e_1, e_2, e_3, e_{12}, e_{13}, e_{23}, e_{t1}, e_{t2}, e_{t3}, i_3, e_{t12}, e_{t13}, e_{t23}, i_{st}\}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $e_{12} = e_1 e_2, e_{t1} = e_t e_1$, etc. The basis vector multiplication satisfies these rules

$$e_k e_l + e_l e_k = 2\epsilon_k \delta_{k,l}, \quad \text{for } k, l \in \{1, 2, 3, t\}, \quad (2.2)$$

with $\delta_{k,l}$ the Kronecker symbol, and $\epsilon_k = +1$, for $k = 1, 2, 3$, and $\epsilon_k = -1$, for $k = t$.

We thus obtain three anti-commuting blades that all square to minus one

$$e_t^2 = -1, \quad i_3^2 = -1, \quad i_{st}^2 = -1. \quad (2.3)$$

Additionally, we get the following multiplication property table Table 1.

TABLE 1. First row: Space-time algebra basis elements e_A .
Second row: Products $e_t e_A i_3$, where e_A is a basis element of $Cl_{(3,1)}$.

1	e_t	e_1	e_2	e_3	e_{12}	e_{13}	e_{23}	e_{t1}	e_{t2}	e_{t3}	i_3	e_{t12}	e_{t13}	e_{t23}	i_{st}		
$e_t()$	i_3	i_{st}	$-i_3$	e_{t23}	$-e_{t13}$	e_{t12}	$-e_{t3}$	e_{t2}	$-e_{t1}$	$-e_{23}$	e_{13}	$-e_{12}$	$-e_t$	e_3	$-e_2$	e_1	1

The general elements of space-time algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ are called multivectors. A multi-vector $M \in Cl_{(3,1)}$ can be represented grade wise as

$$M = \underbrace{M_\emptyset}_{\text{scalar part}} + \underbrace{\sum_{k \in \{t, 1, 2, 3\}} M_k e_k}_{\text{vector part}} + \underbrace{\sum_{|A|=2} M_A e_A}_{\text{bivector part}} + \underbrace{M_{123} i_3 + M_{t12} e_{t12} + M_{t13} e_{t13} + M_{t23} e_{t23}}_{\text{trivector part}} + \underbrace{M_{st} i_{st}}_{\text{quadrivector part}}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $A \subset \{t, 1, 2, 3\}$, and $M_A \in \mathbb{R}$. We thus can express every space-time algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ -valued function f in the form

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_A f_A(\mathbf{x}) e_A, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, \quad (2.5)$$

where the components f_A , are real-valued functions, and e_A are the basis elements of $Cl_{(3,1)}$ given by (2.1). Also by (2.4), every multivector $f \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, can be written as

$$f = \sum_{k=0}^{k=4} \langle f \rangle_k = \langle f \rangle_0 + \langle f \rangle_1 + \langle f \rangle_2 + \langle f \rangle_3 + \langle f \rangle_4, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\langle f \rangle_k = \sum_{|A|=k} f_A e_A$, denotes the grade k -vector part of f .

The principal reverse \widetilde{M} of $M \in Cl_{(3,1)}$ is given by [1, 2, 3, 25]

$$\widetilde{M} = \sum_{k=0}^{k=4} (-1)^{\frac{k(k-1)}{2}} \overline{\langle M \rangle_k}, \quad (2.7)$$

where \overline{M} means to change in the basis decomposition of M the sign of every vector of negative square $\overline{e_{\alpha_1} e_{\alpha_2} \dots e_{\alpha_k}} = \epsilon_{\alpha_1} e_{\alpha_1} \dots \epsilon_{\alpha_k} e_{\alpha_k}$, where $e_{\alpha_1} e_{\alpha_2} \dots e_{\alpha_k}$ is a grade k basis element of $Cl_{(3,1)}$.

It is straightforward to verify that the principal reverse is involutive and anti-automorphic, i.e.

$$\widetilde{\widetilde{M}} = M \quad \text{and} \quad \widetilde{MN} = \widetilde{N}\widetilde{M}, \quad \forall M, N \in Cl_{(3,1)}. \quad (2.8)$$

The scalar part of a space-time multi vector M is defined as

$$Sc(M) = \langle M \rangle_0. \quad (2.9)$$

The following cyclic multiplication symmetry holds true

$$Sc(MNR) = Sc(RMN), \quad \forall M, N, R \in Cl_{(3,1)}. \quad (2.10)$$

For $f, g \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, the scalar product $f * \widetilde{g}$, is defined by

$$f * \widetilde{g} = Sc(f\widetilde{g}) = \langle f\widetilde{g} \rangle_0 = \sum_A f_A g_A, \quad (2.11)$$

particularly, if $f = g$, we obtain the modulus of a multi-vector $f \in Cl_{(3,1)}$ as

$$|f| = \sqrt{f * \widetilde{f}} = \sqrt{\sum_A f_A^2}. \quad (2.12)$$

(2.11) leads consequently to a Cauchy-Schwarz inequality (See Appendix of [23])

$$|f * \widetilde{g}| \leq |f||g|, \quad f, g \in Cl_{(3,1)}. \quad (2.13)$$

Moreover, we define the inner product (f, g) and the scalar product $\langle f, g \rangle$ of two functions $f, g : \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)} \rightarrow Cl_{(3,1)}$ by

$$(f, g) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f(\mathbf{x}) \widetilde{g}(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x} = \sum_{A, B} e_A e_B \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_A(\mathbf{x}) g_B(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad (2.14)$$

and

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f(\mathbf{x}) * \widetilde{g}(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x} = \sum_A \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_A(\mathbf{x}) g_A(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad (2.15)$$

respectively.

For $1 \leq a < \infty$, the linear spaces $L^a(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)}$ are introduced as:

$$\begin{aligned} L^a(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)} &= \{ \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)} \rightarrow Cl_{(3,1)} : \|f\|_a \\ &= \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})|^a d^4\mathbf{x} \right)^{\frac{1}{a}} < \infty \}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

For $a = \infty$, $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)}$ is the collection of essentially bounded measurable functions with the norm $\|f\|_\infty = \text{ess sup}_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})|$. If $f \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)}$ is continuous, then $\|f\|_\infty = \text{sup}_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})|$.

We denote by $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)}$, the Schwartz space of C^∞ space-time functions f , from $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ to $Cl_{(3,1)}$, such that for all $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$\text{sup}_{\substack{\mathbf{x}=(t,x,y,z) \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)} \\ \alpha_t + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 \leq n}} \left((1 + |\mathbf{x}|)^m \left| \frac{\partial^{\alpha_t + \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_3}}{\partial t^{\alpha_t} \partial x^{\alpha_1} \partial y^{\alpha_2} \partial z^{\alpha_3}} f(\mathbf{x}) \right| \right) < \infty, \quad (2.17)$$

where $(\alpha_t, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3) \in \mathbb{N}^4$.

As a consequence of the scalar product (2.15), we get the following space-time Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, a space-time vector modulus identity and a generalization of Euler’s formula.

Lemma 1. *Cauchy–Schwarz inequality. Let f and g be arbitrary space-time functions $\in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}), Cl_{(3,1)}$. Then*

$$\left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \text{Sc}(f(\mathbf{x})\overline{g(\mathbf{x})}) d^4\mathbf{x} \right]^2 \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4\mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |g(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4\mathbf{x}. \quad (2.18)$$

Proof. Assume that $g \neq 0$. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ be given by $\alpha = \frac{\langle f, g \rangle}{\|g\|^2}$, then

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq \|f - \alpha g\|_2^2 = \langle f - \alpha g, f - \alpha g \rangle \\ &= \langle f, f \rangle - \langle f, \alpha g \rangle - \langle \alpha g, f \rangle + \langle \alpha g, \alpha g \rangle \\ &= \langle f, f \rangle - 2\alpha \langle f, g \rangle + \alpha^2 \langle g, g \rangle \\ &= \|f\|^2 - 2 \frac{\langle f, g \rangle^2}{\|g\|^2} + \frac{\langle f, g \rangle^2}{\|g\|^4} \|g\|^2 = \|f\|^2 - \frac{\langle f, g \rangle^2}{\|g\|^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.19)$$

where we used \mathbb{R} -linearity and the symmetry of \langle, \rangle in the third equality.

Therefore $|\langle f, g \rangle| \leq \|f\|_2 \|g\|_2$, or

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \text{Sc}(f(\mathbf{x})\overline{g(\mathbf{x})}) d^4\mathbf{x} \\ &\leq \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4\mathbf{x} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |g(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4\mathbf{x} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

□

Lemma 2. *Let $\mathbf{x} = (t, \vec{x}) \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, with $\vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$. Then we have*

$$|\mathbf{x}|^2 = \sum_{i=0}^3 (e_i \cdot \mathbf{x})^2, \quad (2.21)$$

where \cdot stands for the scalar product in \mathbb{R}^4 , and $e_0 = e_t$. Indeed, $e_t \cdot \mathbf{x} = t$ and $e_i \cdot \mathbf{x} = x_i$, $i = 1, 2, 3$.

Lemma 3. *Let $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\mu \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, with $\mu^2 = -1$. Then we have the following natural generalization of Euler's formula for space-time algebra*

$$e^{\theta\mu} = \cos(\theta) + \mu \sin(\theta). \quad (2.22)$$

Proof. Because $\mu^2 = -1$, we have for any real θ

$$\begin{aligned} e^{\theta\mu} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\theta\mu)^k}{k!} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{\theta^{2k}}{(2k)!} + \mu \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{\theta^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} \\ &= \cos(\theta) + \mu \sin(\theta). \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

We furthermore have useful anti-commutation and modulus relationships.

Lemma 4. *Let e_A be a basis element of $Cl_{(3,1)}$, and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$. Then*

$$e_A e_t = e_t e_A \implies e_A e^{\theta e_t} = e^{\theta e_t} e_A, \quad (2.24)$$

and

$$e_A e_t = -e_t e_A \implies e_A e^{\theta e_t} = e^{-\theta e_t} e_A. \quad (2.25)$$

Proof. Let us prove the second implication, the first one is obtained similarly.

$$\begin{aligned} e_A e^{\theta e_t} &\stackrel{(2.22)}{=} e_A (\cos(\theta) + e_t \sin(\theta)) \stackrel{\text{assumption}}{=} \cos(\theta) e_A - \sin(\theta) e_t e_A \\ &= \cos(-\theta) e_A + \sin(-\theta) e_t e_A = e^{-\theta e_t} e_A. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

Lemma 5. *Let $\theta, \theta' \in \mathbb{R}$, and $\lambda \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, then*

$$\left| e^{-e_t \theta} \lambda e^{-i_3 \theta'} \right| = |\lambda|. \quad (2.27)$$

Proof. Direct computation gives

$$\begin{aligned} \left| e^{-e_t \theta} \lambda e^{-i_3 \theta'} \right|^2 &\stackrel{(2.12)}{=} Sc(e^{-e_t \theta} \lambda e^{-i_3 \theta'} e^{-e_t \theta} \widetilde{\lambda e^{-i_3 \theta'}}) \\ &\stackrel{(2.8)}{=} Sc(e^{-e_t \theta} \lambda \underbrace{e^{-i_3 \theta'} e^{i_3 \theta'}}_{=1} \widetilde{\lambda} e^{e_t \theta}) \\ &\stackrel{(2.10)}{=} Sc(e^{e_t \theta} e^{-e_t \theta} \lambda \widetilde{\lambda}) = Sc(\lambda \widetilde{\lambda}) = |\lambda|^2. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (2.28)$$

2.1. The space-time split

In [9], the \pm split for space-time algebra (space-time split) was introduced as follows:

$$M_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2}(M \pm e_t M i_3), \quad M = M_+ + M_-. \quad (2.29)$$

This provides a new modulus identity.

Lemma 6. *For every $M \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, we have*

$$|M|^2 = |M_+|^2 + |M_-|^2. \quad (2.30)$$

Proof. Using Table 1 we find after a long but straightforward calculation that

$$\begin{aligned}
2M_{\pm} &= M \pm e_t M i_3 \\
&= M_{\emptyset} \pm M_{st} + (M_t \mp M_{123})e_t + (M_1 \pm M_{t23})e_1 \\
&\quad + (M_2 \mp M_{t13})e_2 + (M_3 \pm M_{t12})e_3 \\
&\quad + (M_{t1} \mp M_{23})e_{t1} + (M_{t2} \pm M_{13})e_{t2} + (M_{t3} \mp M_{12})e_{t3} + (M_{12} \mp M_{t3})e_{12} \\
&\quad + (M_{13} \pm M_{t2})e_{13} + (M_{23} \mp M_{t1})e_{23} + (M_{123} \mp M_t)i_3 + (M_{st} \pm M_{\emptyset})i_{st} \\
&\quad + (M_{t12} \pm M_3)e_{t12} + (M_{t13} \mp M_2)e_{t13} + (M_{t23} \pm M_1)e_{t23}. \tag{2.31}
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, by (2.12) we get

$$\begin{aligned}
4|M_{\pm}|^2 &= \\
&(M_{\emptyset} \pm M_{st})^2 + (M_t \mp M_{123})^2 + (M_1 \pm M_{t23})^2 + (M_2 \mp M_{t13})^2 + (M_3 \pm M_{t12})^2 \\
&+ (M_{t1} \mp M_{23})^2 + (M_{t2} \pm M_{13})^2 + (M_{t3} \mp M_{12})^2 + (M_{12} \mp M_{t3})^2 \\
&+ (M_{13} \pm M_{t2})^2 + (M_{23} \mp M_{t1})^2 + (M_{123} \mp M_t)^2 + (M_{st} \pm M_{\emptyset})^2 \\
&+ (M_{t12} \pm M_3)^2 + (M_{t13} \mp M_2)^2 + (M_{t23} \pm M_1)^2. \tag{2.32}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&4(|M_+|^2 + |M_-|^2) \\
&= 4(M_{\emptyset}^2 + \sum_{k \in \{t,1,2,3\}} M_k^2 + \sum_{|A|=2} M_A^2 + M_{123}^2 + M_{t12}^2 + M_{t13}^2 + M_{t23}^2 + M_{st}^2) \\
&= 4|M|^2. \quad \square \tag{2.33}
\end{aligned}$$

The next lemma states that the scalar part of the mixed split products $M_{\mp} \widetilde{N}_{\pm}$ of two space-time multivectors M and N is equal to zero.

Lemma 7. (*Scalar part of mixed split product*). *Given any two multi-vectors $M, N \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, the space-time split is orthogonal in the sense that*

$$Sc(M_{\mp} \widetilde{N}_{\pm}) = 0. \tag{2.34}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
Sc(M_{\mp} \widetilde{N}_{\pm}) &= Sc\left(\frac{1}{2}(M \mp e_t M i_3) \frac{1}{2}(\widetilde{N \pm e_t N i_3})\right) \\
&\stackrel{(2.8)}{=} \frac{1}{4} Sc((M \mp e_t M i_3)(\widetilde{N \pm i_3 \widetilde{N} \widetilde{e}_t})) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} Sc(M \widetilde{N} \pm M i_3 \widetilde{N} \widetilde{e}_t \mp e_t M i_3 \widetilde{N} - e_t M \widetilde{N} \widetilde{e}_t) \\
&= \frac{1}{4} [Sc(M \widetilde{N}) \pm Sc(M i_3 \widetilde{N} e_t) \mp Sc(e_t M i_3 \widetilde{N}) + Sc(e_t M \widetilde{N} e_t)] \\
&= \frac{1}{4} [Sc(M \widetilde{N}) - Sc(M \widetilde{N}) \pm Sc(M i_3 \widetilde{N} e_t) \mp Sc(M i_3 \widetilde{N} e_t)], \tag{2.35}
\end{aligned}$$

where we used $i_3 \widetilde{i_3} = i_3(-i_3) = 1$ for the third equality, linearity of Sc , $\widetilde{i_3} = -i_3$ and $\widetilde{e}_t = -e_t$ for the fourth equality. The last equality is obtained by applying (2.10) and $e_t^2 = -1$. Hence we get (2.34). \square

Lemma 8. *We have*

$$e_t M_+ = -M_+ i_3 \quad \text{as well as} \quad e_t M_- = M_- i_3. \quad (2.36)$$

Proof. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} 2e_t M_{\pm} &= e_t(M \pm e_t M i_3) = \mp M i_3 + e_t M \\ &= \mp (M \pm e_t M i_3) i_3 = \mp 2M_{\pm} i_3. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (2.37)$$

Proposition 9.

$$M_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} \{e_t A_{\pm} (1 \pm i_{st}) + e_t B_{\pm} (1 \mp i_{st})\}, \quad (2.38)$$

where $A_{\pm} = (M_{t12} \pm M_3)e_{12} + (M_{t13} \mp M_2)e_{13} + (M_{t23} \pm M_1)e_{23} + (M_t \mp M_{123})$,
and $B_{\pm} = (M_{t1} \mp M_{23})e_1 + (M_{t2} \pm M_{13})e_2 + (M_{t3} \mp M_{12})e_3 + (M_{st} \pm M_{\emptyset})i_3$.

Proof. In view of relation (2.31), we can easily compute

$$\begin{aligned} 2M_{\pm} &= e_t \{ (M_{t1} \mp M_{23})e_1 + (M_{t2} \pm M_{13})e_2 + (M_{t3} \mp M_{12})e_3 \\ &\quad + (M_{st} \pm M_{\emptyset})i_3 + (M_{t12} \pm M_3)e_{12} + (M_{t13} \mp M_2)e_{13} \\ &\quad + (M_{t23} \pm M_1)e_{23} + (M_t \mp M_{123}) \} \\ &\quad \pm e_t \{ (M_{t12} \pm M_3)e_{12} + (M_{t13} \mp M_2)e_{13} + (M_{t23} \pm M_1)e_{23} \\ &\quad - (M_{t1} \mp M_{23})e_1 - (M_{t2} \pm M_{13})e_2 - (M_{t3} \mp M_{12})e_3 \\ &\quad - (M_{st} \pm M_{\emptyset})i_3 + (M_t \mp M_{123}) \} i_{st} \\ &= e_t \{ A_{\pm} + B_{\pm} \} \pm e_t \{ A_{\pm} - B_{\pm} \} i_{st} \\ &= e_t A_{\pm} (1 \pm i_{st}) + e_t B_{\pm} (1 \mp i_{st}). \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (2.39)$$

3. The space-time Fourier transform (SFT)

The SFT is a non-commutative multi-vector Fourier transform which acts on functions from $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ to Clifford geometric algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$. It was first defined in [9] starting with an isomorphism of quaternions \mathbb{H} to a Clifford geometric volume-time subalgebra. In this section, we briefly recall the space-time Fourier transform definition and its main properties. For more details, we refer the reader to [9, 11, 19]. Furthermore, we add several new results about the SFT.

Definition. Let $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, then the space-time Fourier transform of f is defined by

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \hat{f}^{\diamond}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad (3.1)$$

where

- Space-time vectors $\mathbf{x} = te_t + \vec{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, $\vec{x} = xe_1 + ye_2 + ze_3 \in \mathbb{R}^3$.
- Space-time frequency vectors $\boldsymbol{\omega} = \omega_t e_t + \vec{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, $\vec{\omega} = \omega_1 e_1 + \omega_2 e_2 + \omega_3 e_3 \in \mathbb{R}^3$.
- Space-time volume $d^4 \mathbf{x} = dt dx dy dz$.
- $\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}$ is the canonical dot product (scalar product) of \vec{x} and $\vec{\omega}$, i.e., $\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} = x\omega_1 + y\omega_2 + z\omega_3$, and $\mathbf{x} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} = t\omega_t + \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}$.

Remark 1. It is worthwhile to observe that the SFT can be seen as a special case of the general steerable two-sided Clifford Fourier transform [17, 18]. Furthermore, we note that the exponential kernel factors in (3.1) do not commute with the space-time function f , something that must always be considered in the establishment of the main properties of the SFT.

Combining the definition (3.1), with (2.4) and (2.24), we obtain the following lemma:

Lemma 10. *If $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, then \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} can be decomposed as*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}(\omega) &= \overset{\diamond}{f}_{\emptyset}(\omega) + e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_t(\omega) + \sum_{i=1}^3 e_i \overset{\diamond}{f}_i(-\omega_t, \vec{\omega}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{|A|=2} e_A \overset{\diamond}{f}_A(\omega) + i_3 \overset{\diamond}{f}_{123}(-\omega_t, \vec{\omega}) + e_{t12} \overset{\diamond}{f}_{t12}(-\omega_t, \vec{\omega}) \\ &\quad + e_{t13} \overset{\diamond}{f}_{t13}(-\omega_t, \vec{\omega}) + e_{t23} \overset{\diamond}{f}_{t23}(-\omega_t, \vec{\omega}) + e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_{st}(\omega) i_3, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2)$$

where all $f_A, A \subset \{t, 1, 2, 3\}$, are real-valued.

3.1. Properties of the Space-Time FT

The SFT satisfies the following properties.

Lemma 11. *Let $f, g \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, with $\mathbf{x}, \omega \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, constants $\xi = \xi_t e_t + \vec{\xi}$, $\mathbf{k} = k_t e_t + \vec{k} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ and $\alpha, \beta \in Cl_{(3,1)}$. We then have:*

- *Left linearity*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\alpha f + \beta g\}(\omega) &= \alpha_{+e_t} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\omega) + \alpha_{-e_t} \mathcal{F}^{-e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\omega) \\ &\quad + \beta_{+e_t} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{g\}(\omega) + \beta_{-e_t} \mathcal{F}^{-e_t, i_3} \{g\}(\omega), \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

with $A_{\pm e_t} = \frac{1}{2}(A \pm e_t^{-1} A e_t)$, $\forall A$ constant in $Cl_{(3,1)}$. In particular, if α, β are in \mathbb{R} , or $\alpha = \alpha_{+e_t}, \beta = \beta_{+e_t}$ we get \mathbb{R} -linearity

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\alpha f + \beta g\}(\omega) = \alpha \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\omega) + \beta \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{g\}(\omega). \quad (3.4)$$

- *\mathbf{x} -Shift property*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{k})\}(\omega) = e^{-k_t \omega_t e_t} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\omega) e^{-\vec{k} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3}. \quad (3.5)$$

- *Modulation property*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{e^{-t \xi_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\xi} i_3}\}(\omega) = \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\omega + \xi). \quad (3.6)$$

For the proof of (3.3) see ([17], Prop. 5.1), the other properties are relatively easy to establish.

The next lemma gives the anisotropic scaling property of the four components of \mathbf{x} .

Lemma 12. *Anisotropic scaling property. For $\alpha, \beta, \delta, \gamma \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$, $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, $f_{\mathbf{p}}(\mathbf{x}) \stackrel{def}{=} f(\alpha t, \beta x, \delta y, \gamma z)$, where $\mathbf{p} = (\alpha, \beta, \delta, \gamma)$, we have*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_{\mathbf{p}}\}(\omega) = \frac{1}{\alpha \beta \gamma \delta} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\} \left(\frac{\omega_t}{\alpha}, \frac{\omega_1}{\beta}, \frac{\omega_2}{\delta}, \frac{\omega_3}{\gamma} \right). \quad (3.7)$$

Proof. By substituting $\xi_t = \alpha t$, and $\vec{\xi} = (\xi_1 = \beta x, \xi_2 = \gamma y, \xi_3 = \delta z)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_{\mathbf{p}}\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &\stackrel{(3.1)}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f((\alpha t, \beta x, \delta y, \gamma z) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3}) d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha \beta \gamma \delta} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-\xi_t \frac{\omega_t}{\alpha} e_t} f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) e^{-(\xi_1 \frac{\omega_1}{\beta} + \xi_2 \frac{\omega_2}{\delta} + \xi_3 \frac{\omega_3}{\gamma}) i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha \beta \gamma \delta} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\} \left(\frac{\omega_t}{\alpha}, \frac{\omega_1}{\beta}, \frac{\omega_2}{\delta}, \frac{\omega_3}{\gamma} \right). \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Remark 2. When the scale factors of \mathbf{p} in (3.7) are the same in all directions of \mathbf{x} , we obtain the uniform scaling property

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f(\alpha \mathbf{x})\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{1}{\alpha^4} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\} \left(\frac{\boldsymbol{\omega}}{\alpha} \right). \quad (3.9)$$

Lemma 13. *Partial derivatives.* For $\mathbf{x} = (t, \vec{x} = (x_1, x_2, x_3))$, $w = (\omega_t, \vec{\omega} = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3)) \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, we assume $f, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, $k = 0, 1, 2, 3$, $x_0 = t$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} f(\mathbf{x}) \right\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \omega_t e_t \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}), \quad \text{and} \\ \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} f(\mathbf{x}) \right\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \omega_k \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) i_3, \quad k = 1, 2, 3. \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} f(\mathbf{x}) \right\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &\stackrel{(3.1)}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3}] d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [e^{-t\omega_t e_t}] f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (-\omega_t e_t) e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \omega_t e_t \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}), \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

where we used integration by parts for the third equality. Similarly, for $k = 1, 2, 3$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} f(\mathbf{x}) \right\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} [e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x})] e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \\ &= - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} [e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3}] d^4 \mathbf{x}, \\ &= - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) (-\omega_k i_3) e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \\ &= \omega_k \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) i_3. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (3.12)$$

Proposition 14. *Inversion formula. For $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, such that $\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\} \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, the inverse transform of the SFT can be computed by:*

$$\begin{aligned} f(\mathbf{x}) &\stackrel{\Delta}{=} \mathcal{F}^{-e_t, -i_3}\{\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}\}(\mathbf{x}) \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

where the vectors \mathbf{x} and $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ represent positions in the space and frequency domains, respectively.

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &\stackrel{(3.1)}{=} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} e^{-\omega_i \xi_i e_t} f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) e^{-\vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{\xi} i_3} e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{\omega_t (t - \xi_t) e_t} f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) e^{\vec{\omega} \cdot (\vec{x} - \vec{\xi}) i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{\omega_t (t - \xi_t) e_t} d\omega_t \right] f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} e^{\vec{\omega} \cdot (\vec{x} - \vec{\xi}) i_3} d\omega_1 d\omega_2 d\omega_3 \right] d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \delta(t - \xi_t) f(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \prod_{k=1}^{k=3} \delta(x_k - \xi_k) d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} = f(\mathbf{x}). \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

In the fourth equality above we used $\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{\omega_t (x_t - \xi_t) e_t} dt = 2\pi \delta(x_t - \xi_t)$, and $\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{\omega_k (x_k - \xi_k) i_3} dx_k = 2\pi \delta(x_k - \xi_k)$, $k = 1, 2, 3$.

Two space-time functions $f, g \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$ are related to their SFT via the Plancherel formula.

Proposition 15. *Plancherel identity. For $f, g \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, we have*

$$\langle f, g \rangle = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \langle \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}, \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{g\} \rangle. \quad (3.15)$$

Proof. It follows from (2.15), the inverse formula given by (3.13), and (2.8) that

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle f, g \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc(f(\mathbf{x})\tilde{g}(\mathbf{x}))d^4\mathbf{x} \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^8} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\omega) e^{\vec{x}\cdot\vec{\omega}i_3} d^4\omega\right. \\
&\quad \left.\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-\vec{x}\cdot\vec{\xi}i_3} \widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi) e^{-t\xi_t e_t} d^4\xi\right) d^4\mathbf{x} \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^8} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\omega) e^{\vec{x}\cdot(\vec{\omega}-\vec{\xi})i_3} \widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi)\right. \\
&\quad \left.e^{-t\xi_t e_t} d^4\mathbf{x} d^4\xi\right) d^4\omega \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^8} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\omega) \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} e^{\vec{x}\cdot(\vec{\omega}-\vec{\xi})i_3} dx dy z\right]\right. \\
&\quad \left.\widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi) e^{-t\xi_t e_t} dt d^4\xi\right) d^4\omega \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^5} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\omega) \left[\prod_{k=1}^{k=3} \delta(\omega_k - \xi_k)\right]\right. \\
&\quad \left.\widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi) e^{-t\xi_t e_t} dt d^4\xi\right) d^4\omega \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^5} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{t(\omega_t - \xi_t) e_t} dt\right] \hat{f}(\omega) \prod_{k=1}^{k=3} \delta(\omega_k - \xi_k)\right. \\
&\quad \left.\widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi) d^4\xi\right) d^4\omega \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \hat{f}(\omega) \delta(\omega_t - \xi_t) \prod_{k=1}^{k=3} \delta(\omega_k - \xi_k)\right. \\
&\quad \left.\widehat{\hat{g}}(\xi) d^4\xi d^4\omega\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} Sc\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \hat{f}(\omega) \widehat{\hat{g}}(\omega) d^4\omega\right) \\
&= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \langle \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}, \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{g\} \rangle. \tag{3.16}
\end{aligned}$$

Where we used $\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{x_k(\omega_k - \xi_k)i_3} dx_k = 2\pi\delta(\omega_k - \xi_k)$, $k = 1, 2, 3$, for the fifth equality, applied the cyclic property (2.10) in the sixth equality, and $\int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{t(\omega_t - \xi_t)e_t} dt = 2\pi\delta(\omega_t - \xi_t)$, for the seventh equality. \square

Note further, that with $f = g$, we therefore have the following version of the Parseval theorem related to the SFT.

Corollary 16. *Parseval theorem.* For $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, one has

$$\|f\|_2 = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}\|_2. \tag{3.17}$$

In signal analysis, Corollary 16 means that the SFT preserves the energy of a signal.

The following lemma states that the SFT of a Gaussian is again a Gaussian.

Lemma 17. *The SFT of a Gaussian. For $f(\mathbf{x}) = e^{-\frac{|\mathbf{x}|^2}{2}}$ we have*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = (2\pi)^2 f(\boldsymbol{\omega}). \quad (3.18)$$

Proof. Direct calculation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \left\{ e^{-\frac{|\mathbf{x}|^2}{2}} \right\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t t \omega_t} e^{-\frac{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2}{2}} e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-e_t t \omega_t} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}} dt \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} e^{-\frac{(x^2+y^2+z^2)}{2}} d^3 \mathbf{x} \\ &= (2\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}} e^{-\frac{\omega_t^2}{2}} (2\pi)^{\frac{3}{2}} e^{-\frac{(\omega_1^2+\omega_2^2+\omega_3^2)}{2}} = (2\pi)^2 e^{-\frac{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2}{2}}. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (3.19)$$

By combining Lemma 17 with uniform scaling (3.9), the following lemma holds.

Lemma 18. *For $a \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{e^{-a|\mathbf{x}|^2}\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2 e^{-\frac{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2}{4a}}. \quad (3.20)$$

An useful property of the SFT is stated in the next lemma, which is needed later to derive Heisenberg's and Hardy's uncertainty principles.

Lemma 19. *We have*

$$\diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_{\pm}\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} \mp t \omega_t)} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad (3.21)$$

as well as

$$\diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x}. \quad (3.22)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} 2 \diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &\stackrel{(2.29)}{=} (\diamond f_{\pm} e_t \diamond f_{i_3})(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t} (f_{\pm} e_t f_{i_3})(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= 2 \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_{\pm}\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} \mp t \omega_t)} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

In the second equality we used (3.1) and linearity of the SFT. For the last two equations we used Lemma 8. \square

Remark 3. Lemma 19 states that the SFT can be split into two quasi-complex forms

$$\diamond f = \diamond f_+ + \diamond f_- . \quad (3.25)$$

We can rewrite $\diamond f_{\pm}$ free of coordinates as

$$\diamond f_- (\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_- e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x}\cdot\boldsymbol{\omega})} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad \diamond f_+ (\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+ e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x}\mathcal{U}_{e_t}\boldsymbol{\omega})} d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad (3.26)$$

where the reflection \mathcal{U}_{e_t} is defined by $\mathcal{U}_{e_t}\mathbf{x} = -e_t^{-1}\mathbf{x}e_t$, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$.

- The SFT of f_- (resp. of f_+ except for the reflection \mathcal{U}_{e_t}) is analogous to a complex four-dimensional Fourier transform where the pseudo-scalar i_3 substitutes the imaginary unit i . However, generally we don't have commutativity between f_- (resp. f_+) and the exponential kernel factor in (3.26).
- We point out that $\diamond f_+$ in (3.22) has formally the same kernel with the flat Minkowski metric product $t\omega_t - \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}$ in the exponent, as the complex space-time Fourier transformations with $\exp\{-i(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} - t\omega_t)\}$, $i \in \mathbb{C}$, which is used for electromagnetic fields and electromagnetic wavelet theory [9].
- More broadly, $\diamond f_{\pm}$ can be considered as an instance of the real Clifford-Fourier transform [14] defined for the Clifford geometric algebra $Cl_{(p,q)}$ by

$$\mathcal{F}^{\lambda}\{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(p,q)}} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-\lambda(\mathbf{x}\cdot\boldsymbol{\omega})} d^n \mathbf{x}, \quad (3.27)$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^{(p,q)} \rightarrow Cl_{(p,q)}$, and $\lambda \in Cl_{(p,q)}$ is a square root of -1 , see [13].

Lemma 20. *The inversion formulas of f_{\pm} are given by*

$$f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})e_t} \diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}. \quad (3.28)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) &\stackrel{(3.13)}{=} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f_{\pm}\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &\stackrel{(3.21)}{=} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} \diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &\stackrel{(2.36)}{=} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})e_t} \diamond f_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}. \quad \square \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

Lemma 21.

$$|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}|^2 = |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f_+\}|^2 + |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f_-\}|^2. \quad (3.30)$$

Proof. The proof can be achieved by using (2.30) and Lemma 19.

The following theorem states that the space-time Fourier transform is uniformly continuous.

Theorem 22. *Uniform continuity of SFT. Let $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$. Then $\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}$ is bounded and uniformly continuous on $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$.*

Proof. In light of Equation (3.1), we obviously have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega})| &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |e^{-e_t t \omega_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}}| d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\stackrel{(2.27)}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})| d^4 \mathbf{x}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

Thus, by assumption we conclude that the SFT of f is bounded. Moreover, by setting $\mathbf{h} = (s, \vec{h}) \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, and again using (3.1), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{h}) - \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| &= \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t(t+s)\omega_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\vec{x} + \vec{h}) \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t t \omega_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \right| \\ &= \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-e_t \omega_t t} [e^{-e_t \omega_t s} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{h} \cdot \vec{\omega}} - f(\mathbf{x})] e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \right| \\ &\stackrel{(2.27)}{\leq} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \left| e^{-e_t \omega_t s} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{h} \cdot \vec{\omega}} - f(\mathbf{x}) \right| d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \left(\left| e^{-e_t \omega_t s} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{h} \cdot \vec{\omega}} \right| + |f(\mathbf{x})| \right) d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\leq 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})| d^4 \mathbf{x}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

In the last two inequalities we have applied the triangle inequality and (2.27). We therefore have shown that

$$\left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{h}) - \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| \leq 2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})| d^4 \mathbf{x}. \quad (3.33)$$

Additionally, let

$$f_h(\mathbf{x}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} e^{-e_t \omega_t t} [e^{-e_t \omega_t s} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3 \vec{h} \cdot \vec{\omega}} - f(\mathbf{x})] e^{-i_3 \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}}, \quad (3.34)$$

and

$$g(\mathbf{x}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 2|f(\mathbf{x})|. \quad (3.35)$$

Since $|f_h(\mathbf{x})| \leq g(\mathbf{x}) \forall \mathbf{x}, h \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ and $\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} g(\mathbf{x}) < +\infty$ because $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, and $\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} f_h(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \forall \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, we get by the Lebesgue dominated convergence theorem that

$$\lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{h}) - \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| = 0. \quad (3.36)$$

This shows that $\overset{\diamond}{f}$ is continuous on $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$. Again, since (3.33) is independent of $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ and $\overset{\diamond}{f}$, the SFT is in fact uniformly continuous on $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$. This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 23. *Riemann-Lebesgue lemma.* If $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, then

$$\lim_{|\boldsymbol{\omega}| \rightarrow \infty} \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = 0. \quad (3.37)$$

Proof. According to Lemma 10 we can restrict ourselves to the case where f is a function in $L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, \mathbb{R})$.

Taking $\mathbf{h} = (\frac{2\pi}{\omega_t}, \frac{\pi}{\omega_1}, \frac{\pi}{\omega_2}, \frac{\pi}{\omega_3})$, and applying the \mathbf{x} -Shift property (3.5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= e^{-\frac{2\pi}{\omega_t}\omega_t e_t} \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) e^{-[\frac{\pi}{\omega_1}\omega_1 + \frac{\pi}{\omega_2}\omega_2 + \frac{\pi}{\omega_3}\omega_3]i_3} \\ &= \underbrace{e^{-2\pi e_t}}_{=1} \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \underbrace{e^{-3\pi i_3}}_{=-1} = -\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}), \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

where we used Euler's formula (2.22) for the second equality.

Combining this result with Definition (3.1) yields

$$\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-t\omega_t e_t} [f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})] e^{-\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x}. \quad (3.39)$$

Further applying (3.31), we can write

$$\left| \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x}) - f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})| d^4 \mathbf{x}. \quad (3.40)$$

Due to the fact that continuous functions with compact support $C_c(\mathbb{R}^4, \mathbb{R})$ are dense in the space of integrable functions $L^1(\mathbb{R}^4, \mathbb{R})$, we can then, for any $\epsilon > 0$, choose a function $g \in C_c(\mathbb{R}^4, \mathbb{R})$, so that $\|f - g\|_1 < \epsilon$.

Now with $f_h(\mathbf{x}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} f(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})$ and $g_h(\mathbf{x}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})$, we have

$$f - f_h = (f - g) + (g - g_h) + (g_h - f_h). \quad (3.41)$$

Then

$$\|f_h - g_h\|_1 = \|f - g\|_1 < \epsilon. \quad (3.42)$$

On the other hand, when $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ is large enough, \mathbf{h} becomes very small, so $g \in C_c(\mathbb{R}^4, \mathbb{R})$ implies

$$\|g - g_h\| = \int_{\mathbb{R}^4} |g(\mathbf{x}) - g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{h})| d^4 \mathbf{x} \rightarrow 0, \quad (3.43)$$

as $h \rightarrow 0$, which completes the proof. \square

In the following, we discuss the SFT of a real-valued radial function and more generally the SFT of a radial space-time function and provide the Hausdorff-Young inequality in the SFT domain.

Proposition 24. *Let f be a function in Schwartz space $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^n)$, and \widehat{f} be its Euclidean Fourier transform given by*

$$\widehat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} e^{-i\boldsymbol{\omega} \cdot \mathbf{x}} f(\mathbf{x}) d^n \mathbf{x}, \quad (3.44)$$

and let $r = |\mathbf{x}|$, $s = |\boldsymbol{\omega}|$, and assume that $f(\mathbf{x}) = F(r)$.

The radial Fourier transform in n dimensions is given in terms of the Hankel transform by

$$s^{\frac{n-2}{2}} \widehat{f}(s) = (2\pi)^{\frac{n}{2}} \int_0^{+\infty} J_{\frac{n-2}{2}}(sr) r^{\frac{n-2}{2}} F(r) r dr, \quad (3.45)$$

where $J_{\frac{n-2}{2}}$ is the $\frac{n-2}{2}$ -order Bessel transform.

Theorem 25. (SFT of a radial real-valued function) Let $f(\mathbf{x}) = F(r)$ with $r = |\mathbf{x}|$, be a real-valued radial function in $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)})$. Then we have

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{1}{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|} (2\pi)^2 \int_0^{+\infty} J_1(|\boldsymbol{\omega}|r) F(r) |r|^2 dr, \quad (3.46)$$

where J_1 is the first order Bessel transform.

Proof. By (2.29), and using the fact that f is real valued one has

$$f_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} (f \pm e_t f i_3) = \frac{1}{2} (f \pm f e_t i_3) = \frac{1}{2} f (1 \pm i_{st}). \quad (3.47)$$

Thus, the linearity of \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} and (3.21) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_+\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) + \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f_-\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} - t\omega_t)} d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_-(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} + t\omega_t)} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (1 + i_{st}) \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-i_3(-t\omega_t + \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})} f(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (1 - i_{st}) \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{-i_3(t\omega_t + \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega})} f(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\stackrel{\text{Prop. 24}}{=} \frac{1}{2} (1 + i_{st}) \frac{1}{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|} (2\pi)^2 \int_0^{+\infty} J_1(|\boldsymbol{\omega}|r) F(r) r^2 dr \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} (1 - i_{st}) \frac{1}{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|} (2\pi)^2 \int_0^{+\infty} J_1(|\boldsymbol{\omega}|r) F(r) r^2 dr \\ &= \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 + i_{st}) + \frac{1}{2} (1 - i_{st}) \right] \frac{1}{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|} (2\pi)^2 \int_0^{\infty} J_1(|\boldsymbol{\omega}|r) F(r) r^2 dr \\ &= \frac{1}{|\boldsymbol{\omega}|} (2\pi)^2 \int_0^{\infty} J_1(|\boldsymbol{\omega}|r) F(r) r^2 dr. \end{aligned} \quad (3.48)$$

Remark 4. Theorem 25 states that the SFT of a real-valued radial function is also a real-valued radial function. More generally, we can extend the validity of this statement to space-time functions $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$.

Proposition 26. The SFT of a radial space-time function in $L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$ is radial.

To prove the above proposition we will use the characterization that a function f is radial, if and only if it is invariant under all orthogonal transformations leaving the origin fixed (i.e. f is a function of distance to the origin only). That is f is radial, if and only if $f \circ T = f$, $\forall T \in O(n)$, where $O(n)$ is the orthogonal group in n dimensions. Moreover, the following lemma is required.

Lemma 27. Space-time signal transformations [9, Thm. 5.4].

The SFT of a space-time functions $f \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$ with a $GL(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)})$ -transformation \mathcal{A} (stretches, reflections, rotations, acceleration, boost) of its space-time vector argument \mathbf{x} is

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f(\mathcal{A}\mathbf{x})\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = |\det \mathcal{A}^{-1}| \left\{ f_+ (\mathcal{U}_{e_t} \overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega}) + f_- (\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \boldsymbol{\omega}) \right\}, \quad (3.49)$$

where $\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}}$ is the adjoint of the inverse of \mathcal{A} .

We now proceed to prove Proposition 26. For any orthogonal transformation \mathcal{A} of the Lorentz group, i.e. the group $O(3, 1)$, we have $|\det \mathcal{A}| = 1$, formula (3.49) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f(\mathcal{A}\mathbf{x})\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \\
&= \overset{\diamond}{f}_+ (\mathcal{U}_{e_t} \overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \overset{\diamond}{f}_- (\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \boldsymbol{\omega}) \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathcal{U}_{e_t} (\mathcal{U}_{e_t} \overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega}))} d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_-(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x} \cdot (\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \boldsymbol{\omega}))} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x} \cdot (\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega}))} d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_-(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{x} \cdot (\overline{\mathcal{A}^{-1}} \boldsymbol{\omega}))} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\
&= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+(\mathbf{x}) e^{-i_3((\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega})} d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_- e^{-i_3((\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathbf{x}) \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\
&\stackrel{(\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{z})}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_+(\mathbf{z}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{z} \cdot \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \boldsymbol{\omega})} \underbrace{|\det \mathcal{A}|}_{=1} d^4 \mathbf{z} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f_-(\mathbf{z}) e^{-i_3(\mathbf{z} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})} \underbrace{|\det \mathcal{A}|}_{=1} d^4 \mathbf{z} \\
&= \overset{\diamond}{f}_+(\boldsymbol{\omega}) + \overset{\diamond}{f}_-(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}), \tag{3.50}
\end{aligned}$$

where we used (3.21) in the second equality, $\mathcal{U}_{e_t} \mathcal{U}_{e_t} = 1$ in the third equality, and variable substitution $\mathcal{A}^{-1} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{z}$ with $d^4 \mathbf{x} = |\det \mathcal{A}| d^4 \mathbf{z}$ in the fifth equality.

Therefore $\overset{\diamond}{f}$ is also radial. \square

Remark 5. Since the Gaussian function is radial, Lemma 17 confirms the result of proposition 26.

We will now prove the Hausdorff-Young inequality for the SFT.

Theorem 28. *Hausdorff-Young inequality associated with SFT. Let $1 \leq p \leq 2$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then*

(i) $\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \in L^q(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, whenever $f \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, and we have

$$\|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}\|_q \leq C \|f\|_p, \tag{3.51}$$

where $C = (2\pi)^{\frac{4}{q}}$.

(ii) $f \in L^q(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$ whenever $\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, and we have

$$\|f\|_q \leq \frac{C}{(2\pi)^4} \|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}\|_p. \tag{3.52}$$

Proof.

(i) According to (3.31) we have

$$|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega})| \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f(\mathbf{x})| d^4 \mathbf{x},$$

and obtain

$$\|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}\|_{\infty} \leq \|f\|_1. \tag{3.53}$$

Thus, the SFT is of type $(1, \infty)$ with norm 1. On the other hand, by (3.17) we see that the SFT is of type $(2, 2)$ with norm $(2\pi)^2$. Consequently, we obtain by the Riesz-Thorin interpolation theorem [22, Thm.

2.1] that the SFT is also of type (p, q) , with norm $M \leq ((2\pi)^2)^{\frac{2}{q}}$.

- (ii) The application of (3.51) and (3.13) yields $\|f\|_q \leq C \|\mathcal{F}^{-e_t, -i_3}\{f\}\|_p$. Because we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{-e_t, -i_3}\{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{t\omega_t e_t} f(\mathbf{x}) e^{\vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega} i_3} d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \overset{\diamond}{f}(-\boldsymbol{\omega}), \end{aligned} \quad (3.54)$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} \|\mathcal{F}^{-e_t, -i_3}\{f\}\|_p^p &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{4p}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\overset{\diamond}{f}(-\boldsymbol{\omega})|^p d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{4p}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\xi})|^p d^4 \boldsymbol{\xi} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{4p}} \left\| \overset{\diamond}{f} \right\|_p^p, \end{aligned} \quad (3.55)$$

where we substituted $\boldsymbol{\xi}$ for $-\boldsymbol{\omega}$.

This proves the desired result. \square

Next, for an arbitrary vector $a = (a_t, \vec{a}) \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, we consider the vector differential in the a -direction defined in [23].

$$a \cdot \nabla = a_t \partial_t + \sum_{k=1}^{k=3} a_k \partial_k, \quad \text{with } \partial_k = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k}, \quad 1 \leq k \leq 3. \quad (3.56)$$

Lemma 29. *Integration of parts.* With arbitrary constant $a \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, $f, g \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} f(\mathbf{x}) [a \cdot \nabla g(\mathbf{x})] d^4 \mathbf{x} &= \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f(\mathbf{x}) g(\mathbf{x}) d^3 \mathbf{x} \right]_{a \cdot \mathbf{x} = -\infty}^{a \cdot \mathbf{x} = \infty} \\ &\quad - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} [a \cdot \nabla f(\mathbf{x})] g(\mathbf{x}) d^4 \mathbf{x}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.57)$$

The proof of Lemma 29 works very similar to the proof of integration of parts [23, Proposition 5]. So we do not reproduce it here.

We further establish the next formulae for the vector differential of SFTs of the split function parts f_- and f_+ .

Lemma 30. *One has*

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_-\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_-(\boldsymbol{\omega}), \quad (3.58)$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_+\}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) = (b_t \omega_t - \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_+(\boldsymbol{\omega}). \quad (3.59)$$

Proof. By using the Equation (3.28) we easily get

$$b \cdot \nabla f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} b \cdot \nabla e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{\omega}) e_t} \overset{\diamond}{f}_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}. \quad (3.60)$$

And in light of

$$b \cdot \nabla e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{w})e_t} = (b_t \omega_t \mp \vec{b} \cdot \vec{w}) e_t e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{w})}, \quad (3.61)$$

we get

$$b \cdot \nabla f_{\pm}(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} e^{(t\omega_t \mp \vec{x} \cdot \vec{w})e_t} [(b_t \omega_t \mp \vec{b} \cdot \vec{w}) e_t \hat{f}_{\pm}(\omega)] d^4\omega. \quad (3.62)$$

After applying \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} to both sides of (3.62) the proof is complete. \square

Lemma 31. For two constant vectors $\mathbf{a} = (a_t, \vec{a})$, $\mathbf{b} = (b_t, \vec{b}) \in \mathbb{R}^4$, and $\mathbf{b}' = (b_t, -\vec{b})$ we have

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (b \cdot \omega)^2 \left| \hat{f}_{-}(\omega) \right|^2 d^4\omega = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{b \cdot \nabla f_{-}\}(\omega)|^2 d^4\omega, \quad (3.63)$$

and

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (b \cdot \omega)^2 \left| \hat{f}_{+}(\omega) \right|^2 d^4\omega = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{b' \cdot \nabla f_{+}\}(\omega)|^2 d^4\omega. \quad (3.64)$$

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{b \cdot \nabla f_{\pm}\}(\omega)|^2 d^4(\omega) \\ & \stackrel{(2.12)}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc(\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{b \cdot \nabla f_{\pm}\}(\omega) \widetilde{\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{b \cdot \nabla f_{\pm}\}(\omega)}) d^4\omega \\ & = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (b_t \omega_t \mp \vec{b} \cdot \vec{w})^2 Sc(e_t \hat{f}_{\pm}(\omega) \widetilde{\hat{f}_{\pm}(\omega)}(-e_t)) d^4\omega. \end{aligned} \quad (3.65)$$

In the last equation, we used Lemma 30, (2.8) and the fact that $\widetilde{e_t} = -e_t$. To finish the proof we use (2.10) and $e_t(-e_t) = 1$. \square

Lemma 32. Let $b \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ and $f : \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)} \rightarrow Cl_{(3,1)}$, be a space-time function. We then have

$$Sc(f b \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}) = \frac{1}{2} b \cdot \nabla |f|^2. \quad (3.66)$$

Proof. According to the definition of $b \cdot \nabla$, we get

$$b \cdot \nabla (f \tilde{f}) = (b \cdot \nabla f) \tilde{f} + f (b \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}) = (f (b \cdot \nabla \tilde{f})) \sim + f (b \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}). \quad (3.67)$$

Hence, we obtain by using $Sc(M + \widetilde{M}) = 2Sc(M)$ for all $M \in Cl_{(3,1)}$, $Sc(f b \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}) = \frac{1}{2} Sc(b \cdot \nabla f \tilde{f})$. Noting that $Sc(b \cdot \nabla f \tilde{f}) = b \cdot \nabla (Sc(f \tilde{f})) = \frac{1}{2} b \cdot \nabla |f|^2$ concludes the lemma's proof. \square

4. Uncertainty principles

The uncertainty principle (UP) plays a significant role in mathematical physics, it has implications in different areas like quantum physics, information processing, signal transmission and -analysis, measurement precision, etc. From the perspective of signal analysis, UP tells us that if one observes

a signal for a limited period of time, one will lose information about the frequencies of which it is composed.

The space-time function f would represent the spatial part of a separable wave function, and its SFT $\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}\{f\}$ the same wave function in momentum space. In this section we study Heisenberg's UP, and Hardy's UP for the SFT.

4.1. Heisenberg's UP

Theorem 33. *Directional 4D space-time UP. We consider two arbitrary constant vectors $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$. If f , $(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})f$ and $(\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) \hat{f} \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ & \geq \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} [(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})^2 F_-^2 + (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathcal{U}_{e_t} \mathbf{b})^2 F_+^2], \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

with energies of the left and right traveling wave packets:

$$F_{\pm} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x}. \quad (4.2)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\
& \stackrel{(2.30)}{=} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_+(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right] \quad (4.3) \\
& \quad \times \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \hat{f}_-(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \hat{f}_+(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \right] \\
& \stackrel{\text{Lem.31}}{=} [\dots] \times \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_-\}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla f_+\}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \right] \\
& \stackrel{(3.17)}{=} (2\pi)^4 [\dots] \times \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} + \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla f_+(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right] \\
& \stackrel{(2.18)}{\geq} (2\pi)^4 \left\{ \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \underbrace{Sc((\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f_- \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_+)}_{=0 \text{ by (2.34)}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \underbrace{Sc((\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f_+ \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_-)}_{=0 \text{ by (2.34)}} d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc((\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f_- \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_-) d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc((\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f_+ \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_+) d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\} \\
& = (2\pi)^4 \left\{ \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) Sc(f_- \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_-) d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) Sc(f_+ \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}_+) d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\} \\
& \stackrel{(3.66)}{=} \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \left\{ \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla |f_+(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\} \\
& \stackrel{(3.57)}{=} \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \left\{ \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) |f_+(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\} \quad (4.4) \\
& = \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \left\{ \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b} |f_-|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 + \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}' |f_+|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\} \\
& = \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \left\{ (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})^2 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f_-|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 + (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}')^2 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |f_+|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \right\}. \quad (4.5)
\end{aligned}$$

In the above we used $\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}$, and $\mathbf{b}' \cdot \nabla (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}'$. \square

Consequently, by setting $\mathbf{b} = \mathbf{a}$ in Theorem 33, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 34. *Uncertainty principle. Assuming an arbitrary constant vector $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, if f , $(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})f$ and $(\mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) \overset{\diamond}{f} \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}, Cl_{(3,1)})$, then the following inequality holds*

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ & \geq \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} [|a|^4 F_-^2 + (a_t^2 - (a_1^2 + a_2^2 + a_3^2))^2 F_+^2]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

In (4.6) equality holds for a Gaussian space-time function of the form $f(\mathbf{x}) = A_- e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}$, where A is a $Cl_{(3,1)}$ -constant, and $\alpha > 0$.

Proof. In order to achieve the proof, we need to prove that there is equality. For $f(\mathbf{x}) = A_- e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}$, such that A is a constant in $Cl_{(3,1)}$, and $\alpha > 0$, by straightforward calculation we can show that

$$\mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla f(\mathbf{x}) = -2\alpha(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})f(\mathbf{x}), \quad (4.7)$$

and

$$\mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 = -4\alpha(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})|f(\mathbf{x})|^2. \quad (4.8)$$

Also $f_+ = 0$, because

$$\begin{aligned} f_+ &= \frac{1}{2}(f + e_t f i_3) = \frac{1}{2}(A_- + e_t A_- i_3) e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2} \\ &\stackrel{(2.36)}{=} \frac{1}{2}(A_- + A_- i_3 i_3) e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2} = \frac{1}{2}(A_- - A_-) e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

So if $f = f_-$, then by (3.30) and Lemma 31, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{ \mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla f_- \}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &\stackrel{(3.17)}{=} (2\pi)^4 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\stackrel{(4.7)}{=} (2\pi)^4 4\alpha^2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &= (2\pi)^4 4\alpha^2 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 \\ &\stackrel{(4.8)}{=} \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \\ &\stackrel{(3.57)}{=} \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{a}|^2 |f_-(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^2 = \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} |\mathbf{a}|^4 F_-^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Since $F_+ = 0$, we can conclude the proof. \square

Now, substituting e_i for \mathbf{a} and e_j for \mathbf{b} in Theorem 33, and using $e_i \cdot \mathbf{x} = x_i$, $e_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega} = \omega_j$, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 35. *Uncertainty principle in spatial case. The Heisenberg position-momentum uncertainty principle is expressed by*

$$(\Delta x_i)^2 (\Delta \omega_j)^2 \geq \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} \delta_{i,j}^2 [F_-^2 + F_+^2], \quad (4.11)$$

the variance in space $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$ and the variance in momentum space are, respectively, given by

$$(\Delta x_i)^2 = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_i \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x}, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \quad (4.12)$$

and

$$(\Delta \omega_j)^2 = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 |\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}, \quad j = 0, 1, 2, 3, \quad (4.13)$$

where $\delta_{i,j}$ is the Kronecker symbol.

Theorem 36. *Assume that f , $x_i f$ and $\omega_i \hat{f} \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)})$, $Cl_{(3,1)}$ for $i = 0, 1, 2, 3$. Then*

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{x}|^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2 \left| \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \geq (2\pi)^4 (F_-^2 + F_+^2). \quad (4.14)$$

Proof. We have by (2.21) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{x}|^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2 |\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &= \sum_{i \in \{t, 1, 2, 3\}} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_i \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_i \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 |\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ &+ \underbrace{\sum_{i \neq j} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_i \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (e_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 |\hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega}}_{\geq 0}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.15)$$

Because $(e_i \cdot \mathbf{x})^2 = x_i^2$, and $(e_j \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega})^2 = \omega_j^2$, applying Theorem 33 gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{x}|^2 |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2 \left| \hat{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|^2 d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} &\geq \sum_{i \in \{t, 1, 2, 3\}} \frac{(2\pi)^4}{4} (F_-^2 + F_+^2) \\ &= (2\pi)^4 (F_-^2 + F_+^2), \end{aligned} \quad (4.16)$$

from which the theorem follows. \square

Theorem 37. *L^p -version of Heisenberg's inequality.*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{x})|^p d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |(b_t \omega_t - \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\omega}) e_t \hat{f}_+(\boldsymbol{\omega}) + (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) e_t \hat{f}_-(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^p d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \right]^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \geq \frac{(2\pi)^4}{2C} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b}) |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

where C is the constant given in Theorem 28.

Proof. A straightforward computation yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} \underbrace{(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{b})}_{=\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x})} |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} &\stackrel{(3.57)}{=} - \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} (\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) \mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla |f(\mathbf{x})|^2 d^4 \mathbf{x} \\
&\stackrel{(3.66)}{=} -2 \int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} Sc((\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f})) d^4 \mathbf{x} \quad (4.18) \\
&\leq 2 \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{x}) f(\mathbf{x})|^p d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}|^q d^4 \mathbf{x} \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.
\end{aligned}$$

In the last inequality we applied (2.13) together with Hölder's inequality. On the other hand, by (3.52) it follows that

$$\|\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}\|_q \leq \frac{C}{(2\pi)^4} \|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}\}\|_p. \quad (4.19)$$

We further have

$$\|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}\}\|_p = \|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f\}\|_p, \quad (4.20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f\} &= \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla (f_+ + f_-)\} \\
&= \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_+\} + \mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla f_-\} \\
&= (b_t \omega_t - \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_+ + (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_-, \quad (4.21)
\end{aligned}$$

where we used (3.58) and (3.58). Therefore we obtain

$$\|\mathbf{b} \cdot \nabla \tilde{f}\|_q \leq \frac{C}{(2\pi)^4} \left[\int_{\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}} |(b_t \omega_t - \vec{b} \cdot \vec{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_+(\boldsymbol{\omega}) + (\mathbf{b} \cdot \boldsymbol{\omega}) e_t \overset{\diamond}{f}_-(\boldsymbol{\omega})|^p d^4 \boldsymbol{\omega} \right]^{\frac{1}{p}}. \quad (4.22)$$

This concludes the proof of the theorem. \square

4.2. Hardy's UP

Motivated by the generalization of Hardy's theorem in terms of the algebra of quaternions (see [8, Thm. 5.3]), we extend Hardy's UP in the following to the space-time domain.

Theorem 38. *Let α and β be two positive constants. Suppose $f \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)})$, $Cl_{(3,1)}$ with*

$$|f(\mathbf{x})| \leq C e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}, \quad \mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^4, \quad (4.23)$$

and

$$|\mathcal{F}^{e_t, i_3} \{f\}(\boldsymbol{\omega})| \leq C' e^{-\beta|\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2}, \quad \boldsymbol{\omega} \in \mathbb{R}^4, \quad (4.24)$$

for some positive constants C, C' . Then, three cases can occur:

- (i) If $\alpha\beta > \frac{1}{4}$, then $f = 0$.
- (ii) If $\alpha\beta = \frac{1}{4}$, then $f(\mathbf{x}) = A e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}$, with space-time algebra constant A .
- (iii) If $\alpha\beta < \frac{1}{4}$, then there are infinitely many such functions f .

Proof. The main idea beyond the proof is to apply Remark 3. According to (2.30) we have

$$|f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x})| \leq |f(\mathbf{x})|, \quad \text{and} \quad \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| \leq \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right|, \quad (4.25)$$

then assumptions (4.23) and (4.24) entail that

$$|f_{\pm}(\mathbf{x})| \leq C e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}, \quad \text{and} \quad \left| \overset{\diamond}{f}_{\pm}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) \right| \leq C' e^{-\beta|\boldsymbol{\omega}|^2}. \quad (4.26)$$

Due to (3.26), and by the proof of Theorem 4.2 given in [20] with substituting i by i_3 , we get

- (i) If $\alpha\beta > \frac{1}{4}$, then $f_{\pm} = 0$. Hence $f = f_+ + f_- = 0$.
- (ii) If $\alpha\beta = \frac{1}{4}$, then $f_+(\mathbf{x}) = A_1 e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}$, and $f_-(\mathbf{x}) = A_2 e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}$, with space-time algebra constants A_1, A_2 . Thus, we have

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = A_1 e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2} + A_2 e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2} = (A_1 + A_2) e^{-\alpha|\mathbf{x}|^2}. \quad (4.27)$$

- (iii) If $\alpha\beta < \frac{1}{4}$, then there are infinitely many such functions f_{\pm} , and in turn infinitely many such functions f .

□

5. Conclusion

In this article, we focused on the space-time Fourier transform (SFT), the generalization of the Fourier transform in the framework of space-time algebra.

Firstly, we reviewed Clifford algebra $Cl_{(3,1)}$ for Minkowski space-time $\mathbb{R}^{(3,1)}$, then recalled the space-time split and studied a new modulus for $Cl_{(3,1)}$ -multivectors.

Secondly, we studied the central notion of the special relativistic (space-time) Fourier transform (SFT) in the framework of $Cl_{(3,1)}$, and investigated its fundamental properties, including Plancherel's theorem, Hausdorff-Young's inequality, uniform continuity, and the Riemann-Lebesgue lemma together with several other new properties.

Thirdly, by applying the space-time split (\pm split of the space-time algebra) we were able to prove the Heisenberg uncertainty principle and derived Hardy's theorem related to the SFT.

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